

Amino acid contents of infant foods

LOURDES BOSCH, AMPARO ALEGRÍA & ROSAURA FARRÉ

Nutrition and Food Chemistry, Faculty of Pharmacy, University of Valencia, Avda.

Vicente Andrés Estellés s/n, 46100, Burjassot, Valencia, Spain. Phone 34 96 3544950.

Fax 34 96 3544954; E-mail: lourdes.bosch@uv.es, amparo.alegria@uv.es,

rosaura.farre@uv.es

The protein quality of three milk-cereal-based infant foods (paps) was evaluated by determining their amino acid contents and calculating the amino acid score. Proteins were subjected to acid hydrolysis, prior to which cysteine and methionine were oxidized with performic acid. Amino acids were determined by reverse-phase high-performance liquid chromatography with fluorescence detection with a prior derivatization with 6-aminoquinolyl-N-hydroxysuccinimidyl carbamate. Tryptophan was determined by reverse-phase high-performance liquid chromatography with ultraviolet detection after basic hydrolysis. Glutamic acid, proline and leucine were the most abundant amino acids, whereas tryptophan and cysteine had the lowest contents. Tryptophan was the limiting amino acid in the analyzed infant foods. A pap serving (250 ml) contributes significantly to fulfillment of the recommended dietary allowances of essential and semi-essential amino acids for infants (7-12 months old) and young children (1-3 years old).

Keywords: Infant foods, amino acids, protein quality, amino acid score

Correspondence: Rosaura Farré, Nutrition and Food Chemistry, Faculty of Pharmacy, University of Valencia, Avda. Vicente Andrés Estellés s/n, 46100, Burjassot, Valencia, Spain. Phone 34 96 3544950. Fax 34 96 3544954; E-mail: rosaura.farre@uv.es

1. Introduction

Infant foods have to provide nutrients in sufficient amounts to permit optimal development and growth, and to prevent diseases. Diets deficient in one or several essential amino acids do not allow normal growth, and an adequate protein supply is thus required. From the fifth or sixth month, an exclusively milk-based diet is gradually widened with the introduction of other foods. Cereals in form of paps prepared with milk are usually one of the first foods added in the diversification of the diet (Casado de Frías et al. 1993; Martínez and Hernández 1993).

The European Commission (1996) and the Committee on Nutrition of the European Society for Pediatric Gastroenterology and Nutrition (ESPGAN, 1981) have established guidelines on protein contents and requirements regarding the amino acid composition of cereal-based baby foods. The criteria for regulating the amino acid composition of these products are established in relation to a reference protein (casein).

The protein amino acid contents and the amino acid score are two widely used parameters in a first approach to protein quality evaluation. These parameters have been evaluated in baby foods with different compositions by several authors (Coli et al. 1976; Abrahamsson et al. 1978, 1979; Blattná et al. 1983; Pellett and Mathew, 1986; Dodd and Ratanani 1988; Mensa-Wilmot et al. 2001; Kannan et al. 2001; Jirapa et al. 2001; Fernández et al. 2002; Suhasini and Malleshi 2003).

Given the low biological value of cereal proteins, paps usually include a variable percentage of milk, which contributes high-quality protein - although the latter can be affected by the thermal treatments applied during food processing. The protein quality of cereal-milk-based paps has been evaluated (Blattná et al. 1983; Pellett and Mathew

1986; Dodd and Ratanani 1988; Jirapa et al. 2001; Suhasini and Malleshi, 2003). However, differences in milk contents and in processing methods can affect the protein quality of the analyzed products. Therefore, the aim of the present study was to evaluate the protein quality of three different milk-cereal-based infant foods by measuring the proteinogenic amino acid contents and calculating the amino acid score.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Samples

Three different milk-cereal-based infant foods (pap A, pap B, pap C) commercially available in Spain and containing 88% skimmed milk and 8.8% hydrolyzed 8-cereal flour (wheat, corn, rice, oat, barley, rye, sorghum and millet) were analyzed. All three had the same composition, except for 0.9% honey in pap B and 1.1% fruit in pap C. Samples from three manufacturing batches of each milk-cereal-based infant food (paps A, B, C) were collected. The samples packed in a 250 ml tetra-pack were stored at room temperature until analysis. The composition of the infant foods (paps A, B, C) as stated on the label was: proteins, 3.7, 3.8, 3.8 g/100 ml; carbohydrates, 17.4, 17.0, 17.1 g/100 ml; and lipids, 3.1 g/100 ml, respectively. The density of the product was 1.08 g/ml.

2.2. Sample preparation and analysis

The amino acid content of each of the samples was measured in quadruplicate by applying the method described in Bosch et al. (2006).

In the case of tryptophan, infant foods (2.289 g) were hydrolyzed according to Viadel et al. (1999).

2.3. Statistical analysis

To detect differences between the three types of analyzed baby foods, one-factor analysis of variance testing and Tukey's posteriori test were applied to amino acid contents. Differences were considered significant when $P < 0.01$. The Statgraphics plus 3.1 statistical package (Statistical Graphics Corporation, Rockville, MD, USA) was used throughout.

3. Results and discussion

The amino acid contents of the analyzed paps, expressed as mg/g protein, are reported in Table I.

[Insert Table I about here]

In the three types of paps, glutamic acid, proline and leucine were the most abundant amino acids, whereas the lowest contents corresponded to tryptophan and cysteine. The amino acid profiles were similar in all three paps, and also similar to the amino acid profile of skimmed milk (Souci et al. 1986), their main component (88%) (see Figure 1).

[Insert Figure 1 about here]

Analysis of variance applied to the amino acid contents shows statistically significant differences ($P < 0.01$) among samples (Table I). For most of the amino acids, differences were found between paps with honey (pap B) and paps with fruits (pap C).

Table II reports the recommended dietary allowances (RDA) for essential and semi-essential amino acids (cysteine and tyrosine) established by the Food and Nutrition Board (2002) for infants (7-12 months) and young children (1-3 years old); that is, the population groups for which these foods are intended.

[Insert Table II about here]

A pap serving (250 ml) makes a significant contribution to fulfillment of the essential and semi-essential amino acids RDA of infants (7-12 months) and young children (1-3 years old), as reported in Table II. To estimate amino acid contribution, the average weights corresponding to 7-12 months (9 kg) and 1-3 years (12 kg) were used (Food and Nutrition Board 2002). The amounts of essential and semi-essential amino acids provided by a pap serving were greater than the daily requirements established for 1-year-old to 3-year-old children, except for tryptophan and methionine plus cysteine. Contributions were lower than recommended in the case of infants (7-12 month) for some amino acids - tryptophan showing the lowest fulfillment of the recommended amount. However, the daily diet of a 7-month-old to 12-month-old infant could, depending on age, include one and a half or two pap servings besides other foods. This would fully satisfy the amino acid RDA (Souci et al. 1986; Belitz and Grosch 1992; Martínez and Hernández 1993).

To assess protein quality of the analyzed infant foods the amino acid score was estimated. The reference protein used in the amino acid score calculation for infant foods elaborated with cereals and milk should be casein (ESPGAN 1981; European Commission 1996). Based on this criterion, tyrosine determined the amino acid score in paps A and C, and tryptophan in pap B containing honey (see Table III). The values obtained were lower than the 70% recommended by ESPGAN and the 80% established by the EU Directive - although in the latter this percentage refers to the added protein (in this case milk), while the protein of the whole product was used in our estimation.

[Insert Table III about here]

The amino acid scores, using as reference the FAO/WHO/UNU (1985) amino acid requirement pattern for 0- year-old to 1-year-old infants and for the preschool age group (age 2-5 years), were also calculated. In the three paps (A, B, C) and for the two considered age groups, the amino acid score was determined by tryptophan (see Table III).

Studies of the amino acid score in cereal-milk-based baby foods are scarce in the literature. In addition, the milk content of this kind of products is variable and in most cases not even reported, making it difficult to compare the values obtained with those previously reported. In all cases, however, including our own study, the limiting amino acids were found to be lysine, sulfur-containing amino acids, threonine and tryptophan, that is, the four essential amino acids cited by the FAO/WHO/UNU (1985) as those likely to limit the protein quality of mixed human diets.

The amino acid score has also been calculated using reference proteins different from that proposed by FAO/WHO/UNU (1985). Blattná et al. (1983), using whole egg protein, found sulfur amino acids (methionine and cysteine) to be the limiting amino acids in milk-cereal-based baby foods. Dodd and Ratanani (1988), in weaning foods consisting of cereal-milk blends, found threonine and sulfur amino acids and/or lysine were the determining amino acids depending on the use of the FAO/WHO (1973) recommended levels or human milk as reference, respectively.

Several authors that used the FAO/WHO/UNU (1985) recommended levels as reference reported lysine to be the amino acid determining the amino acid score in weaning foods. Pellett and Mathew (1986) reported amino acid scores of 57-61 for weaning foods based on millet with skimmed milk powder, versus 83-88 for weaning food based on rice with skimmed milk powder. The content of skimmed milk powder in

these products is not known, but it was probably low, because the amino acid score is determined by lysine - the limiting amino acid in cereals. Suhasini and Malleshi (2003) determined the amino acid contents, except tryptophan and tyrosine, in wheat-based and chickpea-based weaning foods containing skimmed dry milk (5%), and also found lysine to be the limiting amino acid. Nevertheless, Jirapa et al. (2001) reported that methionine plus cysteine determine an amino acid score of 48-49 in weaning foods containing cereals, fruits and skimmed milk powder (15%). The reported results indicated that in cereal-milk-based baby foods the milk content can modify the limiting amino acid of the product.

In previous studies, tryptophan or sulfur amino acids and/or tryptophan were found to be the limiting factor in milk-based infant formulas (Pompei et al. 1987; Sarwar et al. 1989; Alegría et al. 1999; Viadel et al. 2000).

4. Conclusions

The three analyzed paps have similar amino acid profiles and are also similar to those of milk, their main component. A pap serving contributes significantly to fulfillment of the RDA of essential and semi-essential amino acids for infants. The amino acid scores estimated using as reference the FAO/WHO/UNU (1985) indicated that tryptophan is the limiting amino acid in the analyzed paps. In milk-cereal-based infant foods the milk content can modify the limiting amino acid of the product.

Acknowledgements- L. Bosch is the holder of a grant from the *Ministerio de Educación y Ciencia*, Spain. Thanks are due to the Generalitat Valenciana for the financial support

given to the Bionutest (group 03/003) and also to Hero España S.A. by providing the samples.

5. References

- Abrahamsson L, Velarde N, Hambraeus L. 1978. The nutritional values of home-prepared and industrially produced weaning foods. *J. Hum. Nutr.* 32: 279-284.
- Abrahamsson L, Bengtsson O, Hambraeus L, Holm H. 1979. Protein quality of milk-cereal based foods for infants and children in relation to processing methods and composition of the products. *J. Food Technol.* 14: 429-440.
- Alegría A, Barberá R, Farré R, Lagarda MJ, López JC. 1999. Amino acid contents of infant formulas. *J. Food Compos. Anal.* 12: 137-146.
- Belitz HD, Grosch W. 1992. Leche y productos lácteos. In: *Química de los Alimentos*. Zaragoza: Acribia. p 540.
- Blatná J, Dostálová J, Eisenberger B, Holasová M, Pickova J, Simova J. 1983. Czechoslovak cereal-based baby foods. *Developments in Food Science*, 5B. *Prog. Cereal Chem. Technol.* 2: 1141-1145.
- Bosch L, Alegría A, Farré R. 2006. Application of the 6-aminoquinolyl-N-hydroxysuccinimidyl carbamate (AQC) reagent to the RP-HPLC determination of amino acids in infant foods. *J. Chromatogr. B.* 831: 176-183.
- Casado de Frías E, Maluenda Carrillo C, Casado Sáenz E. 1993. Alimentación del niño. In: *Nutricion y Dietética. Aspectos sanitarios*. Tomo 1. Madrid: Consejo General de Colegios Oficiales de Farmacéuticos. pp 383-403.

- Coli R, Alberti Fidanza A, Simonetti MS, Vecchiarelli A. 1976. Composizione chimica e qualità proteica di alcuni alimenti omogeneizzati e liofilizzati per la prima infanzia. Riv. Sci. Tecn. Alim. Nutr. Um. 6: 267-272.
- Dodd NS, Ratanani J. 1988. Protein content and amino acid profile of selected commercial infant and weaning foods. J. Food Sci. Technol.25: 317-318.
- ESPGAN. 1981. Guidelines on infant nutrition: recommendations for the composition of a follow-up formula and for the Beikost. Acta Paed. Scand. 287: 39-46.
- European Commission. 1996. Directive 96/5/EC of 16 February 1996 on processed cereal-based foods and baby foods for infants and young. Off J Eur Commun L49:17-28.
- FAO/WHO. 1973. Adhoc Expert Committee on Energy and Protein Requirement. WHO Technical Report Series 522. Geneva: Switzerland.
- FAO/WHO/UNU. 1985. Energy and Protein Requirement. Report of a Joint FAO/WHO/UNU Expert Consultation. WHO Technical Report Series 724. Geneva: Switzerland.
- Fernández DR, Vanderjagt DJ, Williams M, Huang YS, Chuang Lu-Te, Millson M, Andrews R, Pastuszyn A, Glew RH. 2002. Fatty acid, amino acid and trace mineral analyses of five weaning foods from JOS, Nigeria. Plant Food Hum. Nutr. 57: 257-274.
- Food and Nutrition Board. 2002. Dietary reference intakes for energy, carbohydrate, fiber, fat, fatty acids, cholesterol, protein and amino acids. Washington, D.C: Institute of Medicine of the National Academies. pp 10.54-10.68.
- Jirapa P, Normah H, Zamaliah MM, Asmah R, Mohamad K. 2001. Nutritional quality of germinated cowpea flour (*Vigna unguiculata*) and its application in home prepared powdered weaning foods. Plant Food Hum. Nutr. 56: 203-216.

- Kannan S, Nielsen SS, Mason C. 2001. Protein digestibility-corrected amino acid scores for bean and bean-rice infant weaning food products. *J. Agric. Food Chem.* 49: 5070-5074.
- Martínez MJ, Hernández M. 1993. Alimentación durante el primer año de vida. In: Hernández M., editor. *Alimentación infantil*. Madrid: Díaz de Santos. pp 43-53.
- Mensa-Wilmot Y, Phillips RD, Hargrove JL. 2001. Protein quality evaluation of cowpea-based extrusion cooked cereal/legume weaning mixtures. *Nutr. Res.* 21: 849-857.
- Pellett PL, Mathew SP. 1986. Protein quality of homemade weaning food mixtures: 2. Amino acid composition versus biological methods. *Ecol. Food Nutr.* 19: 41-49.
- Pompei C, Rossi M, Mare F. 1987. Protein quality in commercial milk-based infant formulas. *J. Food Qual* 10: 375-391.
- Sarwar G, Botting HG, Peace RW. 1989. Amino acid rating method for evaluating protein adequacy of infant formulas. *J. Assoc. Off. Anal. Chem.* 72: 622-626.
- Souci SW, Fachmann W, Kraut H. 1986. *Food composition and nutrition tables 1986/87*. Stuttgart, Germany: Wissenschaftliche Verlagsgesellschaft mbH. p.20.
- Suhasini AW, Malleshi NG. 2003. Nutritional and carbohydrate characteristics of wheat and chickpea based weaning foods. *Int. J. Food Sci. Nutr.* 54: 181-187.
- Viadel B, Alegría A, Barberá R, Farré R, Lagarda MJ. 1999. Evaluación de un método para la determinación por CLAR de triptófano en fórmulas para lactantes. *Alimentaria*. 303:165-167.
- Viadel B, Alegría A, Farré R, Abellán P, Romero F. 2000. Amino acid profile of milk-based infant formulas. *Int. J. Food Sci. Nutr.* 51: 367-372.

Table I. Amino acid contents of analyzed milk-cereal-based infant foods.

Amino acid	Pap A	Pap B	Pap C
Asp	81.3±1.6 ^a	81.1±1.5 ^a	75.3±5.4 ^a
Ser	62.8±3.6 ^a	61.8±2.2 ^a	57.0±2.9 ^a
Glu	278.8±0.5 ^{ab}	280.6±5.6 ^a	246.1±16.6 ^b
Gly	29.2±0.4 ^{ab}	30.7±1.6 ^a	26.4±1.1 ^b
His	30.8±0.7 ^a	31.3±0.7 ^a	27.5±1.1 ^b
Arg	42.7±2.1 ^{ab}	46.0±2.2 ^a	37.8±1.5 ^b
Thr	45.7±1.2 ^{ab}	46.0±0.8 ^a	41.6±1.8 ^b
Ala	39.5±1.1 ^{ab}	40.1±1.2 ^a	35.7±1.4 ^b
Pro	116.5±5.1 ^{ab}	117.1±3.8 ^a	101.4±5.2 ^b
Tyr	19.7±0.2 ^a	35.4±0.6 ^b	30.3±1.9 ^c
Val	70.2±2.0 ^a	67.8±1.7 ^a	60.2±3.0 ^b
Lys	76.2±1.4 ^a	73.8±2.4 ^a	67.6±3.6 ^a
Ile	56.4±0.6 ^{ab}	60.4±2.3 ^a	49.6±3.3 ^b
Leu	104.9±1.6 ^a	103.2±2.3 ^a	94.0±6.4 ^a
Phe	55.7±0.4 ^{ab}	55.1±1.3 ^a	49.2±3.3 ^b
Cys	10.5±0.8 ^a	10.4±0.1 ^a	10.0±0.2 ^a
Met	24.9±2.0 ^a	18.9±0.1 ^b	24.3±0.6 ^a
Trp	10.0±1.2 ^a	9.7±0.3 ^a	8.8±0.6 ^a

Reported values are the mean±standard deviation (mg/g protein) of three different batches analyzed in quadruplicate. Pap A, milk-cereal-based infant food; pap B, milk-cereal-based infant food with 0.9% honey; pap C, milk-cereal-based infant food with 1.1% fruits. Non-coincidence in the superscripts letters in a row indicates significant differences ($P<0.01$).

Table II. Recommended dietary allowance (RDA) for amino acids for infants (7-12 months old) and young children (1-3 years old) (Food and Nutrition Board 2002) and percentages of RDA fulfilment provided by a 250 ml pap serving.

Amino acid	RDA (mg/kg/day)	Pap A	Pap B	Pap C
7-12 months old				
His	32	98	103	90
Thr	49	95	98	89
Val	58	123	123	109
Lys	89	87	87	80
Ile	43	134	147	121
Leu	93	115	116	106
Phe+Tyr	84	92	113	99
Met+Cys	43	84	71	84
Trp	13	78	78	71
1-3 years old				
His	21	112	117	103
Thr	32	109	113	102
Val	37	145	144	128
Lys	58	100	100	92
Ile	28	154	170	139
Leu	63	127	129	117
Phe+Tyr	54	107	132	116
Met+Cys	28	97	82	97
Trp	8	96	96	87

Pap A, milk-cereal-based infant food; pap B, milk-cereal-based infant food with 0.9% honey; pap C, milk-cereal-based infant food with 1.1% fruits.

Table III. Amino acid scores and limiting amino acid, taking casein as reference protein (ESPGAN 1981; European Commission 1996) and using the FAO/WHO/UNU (1985) amino acid requirement pattern.

Pap	ESPGAN (1981) and European Commission (1996)	FAO/WHO/UNU (1985)	
		0-1 year	2-5 year
A	34.0 Tyr	58.8 Trp	90.9 Trp
B	60.7 Trp	57.1 Trp	88.3 Trp
C	52.2 Tyr	52.1 Trp	80.5 Trp

Pap A, milk-cereal-based infant food; pap B, milk-cereal-based infant food with 0.9% honey; pap C, milk-cereal-based infant food with 1.1% fruits.

Figure 1. Amino acid profile of analyzed paps (A, B and C) and milk.

